

Digital Curation Certificate and Master's Degree Programs

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Introduction

This document describes digital curation certificate and master's degree programs in North America, identifying those that are online. It does not cover individualized certificate programs, such as those at [Indiana University Bloomington](#) or the [University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign](#). Nor does it cover digital curation specializations within MLS and other master's degree programs in iSchools. It is alphabetized by the name of the granting university or other organization. It is available as a [website](#) and a [website PDF with live links](#).

Dedication

In memory of [Paul Evan Peters](#) (1947-1996), founding Executive Director of the Coalition for Networked Information, whose visionary leadership at the dawn of the Internet era fostered the development of scholarly electronic publishing.

Certificate Programs

[Certificate in Digital Curation](#), School of Information Studies, Dominican University

Eligibility: current graduate students in MLIS, MSIM, or MPS programs or post-graduate degree holders. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: 15 credit hours. Course list on program description page.

[Certificate in Digital Curation](#), Krieger School of Arts and Sciences, Johns Hopkins University.

Eligibility: current and aspiring cultural heritage professionals. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: five online courses and onsite internship. [Course List](#). Online.

[Certificate in Digital Curation](#), Library Juice Academy

Click on Eligibility: contact program. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: six courses. Course list on program description page. Online.

School of Information Studies, McGill University, [Graduate Certificate in Digital Archives Management](#)

Eligibility: Bachelor's degree. [Other requirements](#). Course/Credit Hours Requirements: 15 credit hours. [Course list](#).

[Conservation and Digital Curation Advanced Certificate](#), School of Information, Pratt Institute

Eligibility: Current School graduate students or MLS or similar degree. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: four courses. [Course list](#).

[Digital Asset Management - Bronze Certificate](#), School of Communication and Information, Rutgers

Eligibility: Determined by program co-directors. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: six courses. Course list on program description page. Online.

[Digital Asset Management - Silver Certificate](#), School of Communication and Information, Rutgers

Eligibility: Bronze Certificate. Determined by program co-directors. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: six courses. Course list on program description page. Online.

[Digital Assets Management Certificate](#), School of Information, San José State University

Eligibility: Current School Master's students. See this [page](#) for other applicants.. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: nine units. Course list on program description page. Online.

[Graduate Certificate in Digital Curation](#), School of Information, University of Arizona

Eligibility: No formal prerequisites. See program description page for further details. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: 15 units and technology requirements. Course list on program description page. Online.

[Digital Curation and Data Management](#), College of Information, University of North Texas

Eligibility: No particular prerequisites, but courses may have them. See program description page for further details. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: 12 credit hours. Course list on program description page. Online.

[Digital Curation Certificate](#), University of Maine

Eligibility: contact program. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: 12-18 credit hours. [Course List](#). Online.

[Digital Curation for Information Professionals Certificate Program](#), College of Information Studies, University of Maryland

Eligibility: contact program. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: three non-credit courses. Course list on program description page. Online.

[Data Curation Certificate](#), School of Information Studies, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee

Eligibility: Preference given to applicants with bachelor's degree in information sciences, computer information systems, computer science, engineering, statistics, or a related field. See program description page for further details. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: 15 credit hours. Course list on program description page. Hybrid, online.

[Certificate in Digital Curation](#), School of Information and Library Science, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Eligibility: contact program. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: 15 credit hours plus master's paper or field experience. Course list on program description page.

Master's Degrees

[Professional Science Master's in Digital Curation and Management](#), School of Information and Library Science, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Eligibility: Bachelor's degree. Further information on this page. No GRE requirement. Course/Credit Hours Requirements: 30 credit hours including culminating experience. [Course List](#). Online.

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